

On the structure of superextensions of doppelsemi-groups

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A family \mathcal{U} of non-empty subsets of a set D is called an *upfamily* if for each set $U \in \mathcal{U}$ any set $F \supset U$ belongs to \mathcal{U} . An upfamily \mathcal{L} of subsets of D is said to be *linked* if $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{L}$. A linked upfamily \mathcal{M} of subsets of D is *maximal linked* if \mathcal{M} coincides with each linked upfamily \mathcal{L} on D that contains \mathcal{M} . The *superextension* $\lambda(D)$ of D consists of all maximal linked upfamilies on D . Any associative binary operation $*$: $D \times D \rightarrow D$ can be extended to an associative binary operation

$$\begin{aligned} * : \lambda(D) \times \lambda(D) &\rightarrow \lambda(D), \\ \mathcal{M} * \mathcal{L} &= \left\langle \bigcup_{a \in M} a * L_a : M \in \mathcal{M}, \{L_a\}_{a \in M} \subset \mathcal{L} \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

A *doppelsemigroup* is an algebraic structure (D, \dashv, \vdash) consisting of a non-empty set D equipped with two associative binary operations \dashv and \vdash satisfying the following axioms:

$$(x \dashv y) \vdash z = x \dashv (y \vdash z) \text{ and } (x \vdash y) \dashv z = x \vdash (y \dashv z).$$

In the talk, we discuss the structure of the doppelsemigroup $(\lambda(D), \dashv, \vdash)$ of maximal linked upfamilies on a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) . In particular, we describe right and left zeros and identities, commutativity, the center, ideals of the superextension $(\lambda(D), \dashv, \vdash)$ of a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) . We introduce *the superextension functor* λ in the category **DSG** whose objects are doppelsemigroups and morphisms are doppelsemigroup homomorphisms, and show that

this functor preserves strong doppelsemigroups, doppelsemigroups with left (right) zero, doppelsemigroups with left (right) identity, left (right) zeros doppelsemigroups. On the other hand, the functor λ does not preserve commutative doppelsemigroups and group doppelsemigroups. Also we show that the automorphism group of the superextension of a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) contain a subgroup, isomorphic to the automorphism group of (D, \dashv, \vdash) .